

Tissue gene expression in animal models of high-fat diet.

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Consumption of a high-fat diet resulted in activation of *Cyp2c44* and *Cyp2c70* concomitant with silencing of *Cyp2f2*. Nutrient sensing component *Tsc22d2* was activated. A high-fat diet was associated with activation of growth differentiation factor *Gdf3*, the chemokine *Ccl7* and neutral cholesterol ester hydrolase 1, encoded by *Nceh1*.

Citations

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